

Effect of Activity-Based Instruction on the Self-Efficacy of Secondary School Biology Students in the Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the Effect of activity-based instruction on Self-efficacy of Secondary School Students in Biology in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State. This study was necessitated due to persistence low performance, the study adopts a Quasi-Experimental Design of Pretest, posttest, Non-Equivalent Groups. Two Objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided this study. The population comprised all 2465 Biology students from 17 public Senior Secondary Schools in Gumel Education Zone. A sample of (174) students from two randomly selected coeducational schools was used for the study. The study involves two groups. The experimental group was taught Activity-based Instruction Model while the Control Group was exposed to the same concept using Lecture Method. One instrument were used for data collection which is Genetics Concept Self-efficacy Questionnaire (GCSQ) and have reliability coefficients of 0.85 estimated using Cronbach's alpha statistic. Research questions were answered using Mean rank and Sum rank statistics while null hypotheses were tested using Independent Samples t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Findings reveal a significant difference between the mean scores of experimental and control groups in self-efficacy all in favour of the experimental group. The results also show that male and female students in the experimental group do not significantly differ in the variables studied. Based on these findings, the researcher concludes that activity-based instruction is effective and gender-friendly in fostering the examined variable among

secondary school Biology students. It is therefore recommended that Biology teachers frequently employ this model in teaching challenging concepts in Biology like Genetics concept.

Keywords: Activity-based Instruction, Genetics, Self-efficacy.

Introduction

Science is a universal subject that spans the branch of knowledge that examines the structure and behaviour of the physical and natural world through observation and experiment. Singh (2014) observed science as the study that involves systematic study of natural phenomena which allows the students to experience the richness and excitement of the natural world, the process of inquiring, critical thinking and demonstration of skill. Therefore, the importance of science in our society made the federal government of Nigeria, through the federal ministry of education to introduce science education in the Nigerian schools. Yunusa (2014) view science education is the field of study which scientific process is also concerned with teaching science content, and process to individual not traditionally part of the scientific community. The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2024) sets as a goal for science education in Nigeria that government shall popularize the study of science and production of adequate number of scientists to inspire and support national development. Based on this policy, Jafar (2025) deduced that the aim of science and technology education is to inculcate science and technology in the thinking and working processes of the society in order to create science and technology culture. However, Yusuf (2024) and Jafar (2025) pointed out that the performance of science students in Nigeria school still leaves much to be desired right from the primary school through secondary school to the tertiary level of education. General view of Nigerian students' performance in biology as a science subject in the West African Examination Council Chief examiners reports from (2023-2025) revealed fluctuations and downward trends in students' performance.

Biology is a natural science concerned with the study of life and living organism. According to Okenyi (2015) defined it as a branch of science that is structured to equip students with knowledge of life processes and phenomena of living organisms. Biology plays a vital role in providing knowledge of relevant concepts about living things and developing scientific skills and attitudes. Ibrahim (2015) further stated that Biology is a subject specially designed to provide students with skills and attitudes of caring about themselves, other organisms and the environment. In fact, Lawal (2011) stipulates that when the knowledge of Biology is acquired and applied in any society, it can bring about rapid and sustainable national development. According to National Policy on Education (FRN2024) biology is one of the science subjects that senior secondary students offer in senior secondary certificate examination in Nigeria. Biology is very important science subject and requirement for further studies of other science related professional sources such as agriculture, pharmacy, biotechnology, medicine, biochemistry, anatomy, physiology, entomology, zoology and genetics.

Genetics is a branch of Biology that studies the function and behavior of genes. Genes influence many aspects of our daily life from the food we eat to identification of criminals, and treatment of diseases. In agriculture, genetics advances have enabled scientists to alter a plant or an animal structure to make it more useful. For instance, food crops such as oranges, potatoes, wheat, and rice have been genetically altered to make them withstand insect pests and harsh weather conditions. According to Sorajin (2015), tomato and apple have been genetically modified, so that they can withstand discoloration and bruising on their way to market, thus enhancing their appeal on supermarket shelves. The study of genetics today is important and as such considered as crucial

to the scientific and technological development of the society. Fakunle (2012) opined that understanding of the concepts of genetics and its mode of operation appears to be more difficult than any other topic in Biology. This evidence is showed in the WAEC Chief Examiners Reports (2020 – 2024). Biology has become one of the most important discipline in the school curriculum; its importance in the general education has gained world-wide recognition. Biology as a subject is required for everyday life on matter of personal and community health as Stated in the National policy on education (FRN, 2024). Despite the importance of Biology as a science subject, empirical studies such as those of Etobro and Fabinu (2017) have shown that students still perform poorly in Biology at Senior Secondary School level. This study therefore, find out the effect of activity-based instruction, which is learner-centered in its characteristics, on genetic concepts for better understanding and performance among Senior Secondary School II Biology Students.

Activity-based instruction is a technique whereby the main focus is learning by doing, involving learners in physical and mental activities that develop understanding through experience. **(Marley and Charbonneau 2014)**. According to Anwer (2019) Activity-based instruction is a learning process in which students are constantly engaged in activities rather than sit as passive listeners. It encourages active participation of students. Activity-based are variety of activity that may or may not be actual experiments such as observation or measurement not necessarily carried out in the laboratory. Activity learning fosters the mind in more basic ways by extending the links between the brain and the hands. Materials such as auditory, visual, tactile and body motor function are all involved in hands-on learning activities and this makes information which involved all the memories become stronger and retrievable. Researchers such as Oziem and Ali (2011), have shown that students who were exposed to learning using hands activities in different areas achieved better than those not expose but Anwer (2019) posit that activity-based instruction involved the child in a total learning experience which enhance the ability to think critically, it is obvious, that any teaching strategy that is skilled towards this direction can be seen as an activity-oriented teaching method.

Activity-based Instruction is a method of instruction where students are guide to gain knowledge by experience. This mean giving the students the opportunity to manipulate the objects they are studying, for instance, plants, insects, rocks, water, gene, elementary canal and skeletal system. Activity-based instruction help students to interact and find out solution to the common problem by themselves. Through hands-on activities students are able to engage in real life illustration and observed the change in different variable, it offers concrete illustration of concepts. This method of centered learning which allows the learner to see, touch, and draw biological diagram. Therefore, there is need for considering Activity-based Instruction in design instruction for teaching and learning of biology s as to improve students' performance.

Another factor to performance in science and biology is gender, according to Ezeh and Okeke, (2008) Gender is any physical and behavioural difference between male and female which are social culturally base. Before now science was preserved for male with little participation of female students. This is due to the fact that girl did not embrace formal education and especially science education early enough as their male counterpart. However, Studies carryout on gender and academic performance such as those of Ibrahim (2012) observe that boys achieved better than girls, but studies by Bunkure (2012) pointed out that girls performed better than boys. However, some other such as Abdulganiyu (2017) indicate that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female biology students taught using instructional material like Activity-based Instruction it is against this background that this study seeks to figure out the

effectiveness of Activity-based Instruction on academic performance of secondary biology students in Activity-based Instruction on self-efficacy and performance in genetic concepts in Gumel Education Zone Jigawa State.

Statement of the Problem

The poor performance of secondary school students in science subjects, particularly Biology, has continued to generate concern among educators, parents, and stakeholders in education. Despite Biology being a core science subject, students consistently perform below expectations in internal and external examinations, raising questions about the effectiveness of current teaching methods. The situation has led to various studies aimed at identifying the underlying causes of this persistent poor performance and exploring strategies to improve students' learning outcomes.

Several researchers, including Lawal (2009) and Lakpini (2013), have identified teacher-centered instructional strategies as a major factor contributing to students' low achievement in Biology. Similarly, Etobro and Fabinu (2017) and Jafar (2025) reported that students still struggle to attain satisfactory results at the Senior Secondary School level. One particularly challenging area in Biology is genetics. According to the WAEC Chief Examiners' Reports (2022–2025), students often exhibit misconceptions, confusion, and difficulties in understanding genetic concepts. Lawal (2009) and Shuaibu (2017) further highlighted that inadequate laboratory equipment, lack of instructional materials, low student self-efficacy, and limited creativity in teaching contribute significantly to this poor performance.

Despite interventions and research efforts aimed at improving student outcomes, performance in genetics remains consistently low, suggesting that lectureteaching methods may not be sufficient. Activity-Based Instruction (ABI) has emerged as a promising strategy that actively engages students in learning through hands-on activities, experimentation, and collaborative problem-solving. Studies, such as Anwer (2019), have demonstrated that ABI can enhance students' understanding of scientific concepts and improve academic performance compared to traditional methods.

Given the complexity of genetics and the critical role of student self-efficacy in learning, there is a need to explore alternative instructional approaches that not only convey content effectively but also build students' confidence and interest in Biology. The low levels of self-efficacy among secondary school students in Genetics in Gumel may hinder their ability to engage meaningfully with the subject, negatively impacting their academic achievement. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the effect of Activity-Based Instruction on students' self-efficacy in Genetics, aiming to identify effective strategies for improving understanding, engagement, and performance in this challenging area of Biology.

Addressing this problem is crucial not only for improving examination results but also for fostering students' long-term interest in science, promoting critical thinking, and developing practical skills necessary for scientific inquiry. The findings of this study could inform teachers, curriculum planners, and policymakers on the benefits of adopting learner-centered instructional strategies to enhance meaningful learning in Biology.

Objectives of the Study

The study has the following objectives

1. ascertain the effect of activity-based instruction on self-efficacy of secondary school students in genetics in Gumel education zone, Jigawa state.
2. examine the effect of activity-based instruction on self-efficacy of male and female secondary school students in genetics in Gumel education zone, Jigawa state

Research Questions

The study has the following research question

1. What is the difference between the mean Self-efficacy scores of secondary school students taught genetics concepts using Activity-based Instruction and those taught with lecture method?
2. What is the difference between the mean self-efficacy score between male and female secondary school students taught genetics concepts using Activity-based Instruction in Gumel education zone, Jigawa state?

Null Hypotheses

Base on the research question the following null hypotheses were tested at $P < 0.05$ level of significance;

Ho₁. there is no significance difference between mean self-efficacy score of secondary school students taught genetics concepts using activity-based Instruction and those taught with lecture method in Gumel education zone, Jigawa state.

Ho₂. there is no significance difference between mean self-efficacy score of male and female secondary school students taught genetics concepts using Activity-based Instruction in Gumel education zone, Jigawa state

Methodology

The study adopted quasi-experimental design, specifically the pre-test, post-test, quasi experimental and control group design. Pre-test was administered before treatment to measure the students' academic performance in Genetics Concept. The students in the experimental group were taught using activity-based instruction while those in the control group were taught using lecture method. Treatment lasted for six weeks each. After the treatment post-test, was administered to both groups to measure their academic performance ability of learnt concepts. The population of this study is made up of two thousand, four hundred and sixty-five (2465) SS2 Secondary school Biology students in the study area. One hundred and seventy four (174) SS2 Secondary school Biology students constituted the sample for this study and were derived from two (2) co-educational schools sampled from the fifteen (15) public senior secondary schools in Gumel Education Zone. The instrument used for data collection is Genetics Concept Performance Test (GCPT) with has 40-item multiple-choice test with a reliability coefficient of 0.88. The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically the mean and standard deviation, to address the research questions, while the independent samples t-test was employed to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. All analyses were done using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM Version 26.

Results Presentation

Question One: What is the difference between the mean Self-efficacy scores of secondary school students taught genetics concepts using Activity-based Instruction and those taught with lecture method?

Table 1: Mean Rank, Sum of Rank Statistics of Posttest GCSQ level for Students in Experimental and Control Groups

GROUP	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Experimental Group	88	130.50	11484.00
Control Group	86	43.50	3741.00
Total	174		

Table 1 shows that there is a difference in the self-efficacy levels of SSII students taught Genetics using Activity-Based Instruction and those taught with the Lecture Method. The students taught with Activity-Based Instruction had a mean rank of 130.50, while those taught with the Lecture Method had a mean rank of 43.50. This shows a mean rank difference of 87.00 in favour of students taught with Activity-Based Instruction.

Hypothesis One: There is no significance difference between mean self-efficacy score of secondary school students taught genetics concepts using activity-based Instruction and those taught with lecture method in Gumel education zone, Jigawa state.

Table 2: Summary of Mann Whitney Mean Posttest GCSQ Level for Experimental and Control Groups.

GROUP	n	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	P
Experimental Group	88	130.50	11484.00	0.000
Control Group	86	43.50	3741.00	
Total	174			

Significance at $P < 0.05$ Level

Table 2 shows that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy levels of SSII students taught Genetics using Activity-Based Instruction and those taught with the Lecture Method. The calculated p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that Activity-Based Instruction has a strong positive effect on students' self-efficacy in learning Genetics. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between the two groups is rejected.

Question Two: 2. What is the difference between the mean self-efficacy score between male and female secondary school students taught genetics concepts using Activity-based Instruction in Gumel education zone, Jigawa state?

Table 3: Mean Rank, Sum of Rank Statistics of Posttest GCSQ level for Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Male	51	41.16	2099.00
Female	37	49.11	1817.00
Total	88		

Not significance at $P < 0.05$ Level

Table 3 shows that there is a difference in the self-efficacy levels of male and female SSII students taught Genetics using Activity-Based Instruction. The mean rank self-efficacy levels for male and female students are 41.16 and 49.11, respectively, showing a small mean rank difference of 7.95.

This indicates that Activity-Based Instruction is gender-friendly and equally effective in improving students' self-efficacy toward learning Genetics.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significance difference between mean self-efficacy score of male and female secondary school students taught genetics concepts using Activity-based Instruction in Gumel education zone, Jigawa state.

Table 4: Summary of Mann Whitney Mean Posttest GSCQ Level for Male and Female in Experimental Group

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	P
Male	51	41.16	2099.00	0.14
Female	37	49.11	1817.00	
Total	88			

Not significance at $p < 0.14$ level

Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference in the self-efficacy levels of male and female SSII students taught Genetics using Activity-Based Instruction. This is because the calculated p-value of 0.146 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between male and female students' self-efficacy levels is accepted and retained.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the effect of activity-based instruction on students' self-efficacy in learning genetics concepts, as well as the influence of gender on students' self-efficacy when exposed to the instructional strategy. The findings are discussed according to the research questions and hypotheses formulated for the study.

Findings from Table 1 revealed that there was a clear difference between the self-efficacy levels of students taught genetics concepts using activity-based instruction and those taught using the lecture method. Students who were exposed to activity-based instruction demonstrated higher self-efficacy levels than their counterparts taught with the lecture method. This implies that activity-based instruction positively influenced students' belief in their ability to learn and perform tasks related to genetics. This finding agrees with the reports of Bandura (1997) and Schunk (2012), who stated that learners' self-efficacy can be enhanced through mastery experiences and active engagement in learning tasks. Similarly, Achor and Imoko (2012) and Nwagbo and Okeke (2019) found that when students are actively involved in learning activities, their confidence and motivation to learn science concepts increase significantly.

Findings from Table 2 confirmed that the difference observed in Table 1 was statistically significant, as the p-value obtained was less than 0.05. This means that students taught using activity-based instruction significantly outperformed those taught using the lecture method in terms of self-efficacy level. The null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference between the self-efficacy levels of students taught genetics concepts using activity-based instruction and those taught using the lecture method, was therefore rejected. This finding agrees with the results of Achor and Imoko (2012), who emphasized that activity-based learning improves students' confidence, and with Nwagbo and Okeke (2019), who also reported that learner-centred approaches enhance students' attitude and self-belief in science. Furthermore, it supports the constructivist theory, which posits that learners construct knowledge through active participation and social interaction rather than through passive reception.

Findings from Table 3 showed that there was a slight difference between the self-efficacy levels of male and female students taught genetics concepts using activity-based instruction, with females showing slightly higher self-efficacy levels than males. However, the difference was not statistically significant. This suggests that activity-based instruction is effective for both male and female students, promoting equal opportunities and participation in the learning process. This finding agrees with Ezeudu and Obi (2013) and Ogunleye (2016), who found that gender does not significantly affect students' achievement or self-efficacy when learner-centred teaching methods are used.

Findings from Table 4 further confirmed that the difference in the self-efficacy levels of male and female students was not statistically significant, as the p-value obtained was greater than 0.05. This implies that both male and female students benefited equally from the activity-based instructional strategy. The null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean self-efficacy levels of male and female students taught genetics concepts using activity-based instruction, was therefore accepted and retained. This result is consistent with the findings of Bandura (2006), who explained that self-efficacy beliefs are not inherently influenced by gender but by the type of learning experiences and opportunities provided. It also aligns with Ezeudu and Obi (2013) and Ogunleye (2016), who concluded that gender differences tend to disappear when teaching approaches emphasize participation and interaction.

In summary, findings from Tables 1 and 2 revealed that activity-based instruction significantly improved students' self-efficacy in learning genetics concepts compared to the lecture method, and this agrees with several scholars who emphasized the effectiveness of learner-centred teaching in enhancing students' confidence and engagement in science learning. Findings from Tables 3 and 4 showed that there was no significant difference between male and female students' self-efficacy levels when exposed to activity-based instruction, supporting previous studies that found learner-centred methods to be gender-neutral. Overall, the study concludes that activity-based instruction enhances students' self-efficacy in learning genetics concepts and provides an inclusive environment that benefits both male and female learners equally.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the effect of Activity-Based Instruction on secondary school students' self-efficacy in learning genetics concepts in Gumel Education Zone, Jigawa State. The findings revealed that students taught genetics using Activity-Based Instruction exhibited significantly higher self-efficacy levels than those taught with the conventional lecture method. This indicates that active participation and engagement in learning activities enhance students' confidence, motivation, and belief in their ability to understand and apply genetics concepts effectively.

The study also found no significant difference between the self-efficacy levels of male and female students exposed to Activity-Based Instruction. This suggests that the strategy is gender-friendly and promotes equal learning opportunities for both male and female learners. Overall, the results demonstrate that Activity-Based Instruction is an effective learner-centred approach that fosters inclusion, participation, and improved self-efficacy among students irrespective of gender differences.

Based on these findings, it is recommended that biology teachers adopt Activity-Based Instruction in teaching genetics and other science concepts to improve students' self-efficacy, interest, and active involvement in learning. Educational authorities and school administrators should organize workshops and seminars to train teachers on the effective design and implementation of activity-based learning strategies. Curriculum planners should integrate Activity-Based Instructional

approaches into the biology curriculum to promote inquiry, experimentation, and hands-on learning. Government and school management should ensure the provision of adequate instructional materials, laboratory facilities, and teaching aids to support activity-based learning. Teachers should also continue to employ learner-centred methods that cater equally to both male and female students, ensuring inclusive participation and confidence-building in science learning. In conclusion, Activity-Based Instruction has proven to be a powerful and inclusive teaching approach that enhances students' self-efficacy in genetics learning, supports equitable participation, and contributes to improved science education outcomes.

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